
Leveraging Marketing Automation to Enhance Customer Relationship Management and Improve Management Performance in MSME B2B

Pitri Yanti^{1*}, Ratih Hurriyati², Puspo Dewi Dirgantari³

Faculty of Economics and Business Education, Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia | pitri0816@upi.edu¹

Faculty of Economics and Business Education, Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia | ratihhurriyati@upi.edu²

Faculty of Economics and Business Education, Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia / puspodewidirgantari@upi.edu³

Correspondence Author*

Abstract

This study aimed to explore the impact of using marketing automation in customer relationship management strategies and ultimately improving management performance in the context of B2B Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). The research method involved primary data collection using a quantitative approach and a non-probability sampling method, specifically purposive sampling, on 105 samples that actively use marketing automation tools. The analysis technique used was Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with the help of Lisrel 8.80 software. The results show that marketing automation has a positive and significant impact on B2B customer relationship management, with reach of message as the most dominant indicator, contributing 65.61%. Furthermore, B2B customer relationship management also has a positive and significant effect on Marketing Performance, where improving the quality of customer relationships is the most dominant indicator at 77.4%, and the most dominant indicator in shaping marketing performance is having a larger market, accounting for 42.25%. The conclusion of this study is that the use of marketing automation in customer relationship management strategies can improve the marketing performance of B2B-based MSMEs.

Keywords: CRM, Marketing Automation, Marketing Performance, MSME B2B

Abstrak

Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk mengeksplorasi dampak penggunaan otomatisasi pemasaran dalam strategi manajemen hubungan pelanggan dan pada akhirnya meningkatkan kinerja manajemen dalam konteks Usaha Mikro, Kecil, dan Menengah (UMKM) B2B. Metode penelitian ini melibatkan pengumpulan data primer dengan menggunakan pendekatan kuantitatif dan metode non-probabilitas sampling, khususnya purposive sampling, pada 105 sampel yang aktif menggunakan alat otomatisasi pemasaran. Teknik analisis yang digunakan

adalah Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) dengan bantuan perangkat lunak Lisrel 8.80. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa otomatisasi pemasaran memiliki dampak positif dan signifikan terhadap manajemen hubungan pelanggan B2B, dengan reach of message sebagai indikator yang paling dominan, menyumbang sebesar 65,61%. Selanjutnya, manajemen hubungan pelanggan B2B juga berpengaruh positif dan signifikan terhadap Kinerja Pemasaran, di mana peningkatan kualitas hubungan pelanggan menjadi indikator paling dominan sebesar 77,4%, dan indikator yang paling dominan dalam membentuk kinerja pemasaran adalah memiliki pasar yang lebih besar, menyumbang sebesar 42,25%. Kesimpulan dari penelitian ini adalah bahwa penggunaan otomatisasi pemasaran dalam strategi manajemen hubungan pelanggan dapat meningkatkan kinerja pemasaran UMKM berbasis B2B.

Kata kunci: CRM, Marketing Automation, Marketing Performance, MSME B2B

Introduction

Business-to-business (B2B) interactions form the backbone of global commerce, with micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) playing a pivotal role in this dynamic landscape. However, B2B MSMEs often encounter challenges in maintaining and fostering customer relationships in the digital era, potentially leading to a loss of trust and hindering long-term sustainability (Humairo & Abidin, 2023). Additionally, the integration of existing technology with emerging digital tools and effective data management can pose significant hurdles due to limited technological expertise. Customer relationship management (CRM) has emerged as a transformative tool for B2B MSMEs to navigate these challenges and embrace digital transformation (Yunusa et al., 2023). CRM empowers MSMEs to effectively manage customer data, track customer interactions, and provide personalized customer service, ultimately enhancing customer relationships and driving sales and marketing effectiveness (Aqiilah, 2022; Latifah et al., 2022; Ramadhani, 2022; Saura et al., 2020).

Despite the potential benefits of CRM, its adoption among Indonesian MSMEs remains relatively low. CRM implementation can be complex and resource-intensive, requiring substantial financial investment and digital literacy. Furthermore, convincing colleagues to adopt changes and overcoming the lack of digital literacy among MSME players can pose additional hurdles (Benjamin, 2019; Corsaro et al., 2021; Hanaysha et al., 2022; Harini et al., 2023; Mero et al., 2022; Parker, 2020).

Marketing automation offers a promising solution to address these challenges. Marketing automation streamlines repetitive marketing tasks, reduces manual labor, and optimizes operational costs. Additionally, it leverages data-driven insights to gain valuable customer information (Harisandi et al., 2023). By synergizing marketing automation with CRM strategies, B2B MSMEs can effectively manage customer interactions, enhance customer satisfaction, and improve overall business performance. This research is based on the limitations of research that focuses on B2B MSMEs because most studies focus more on large companies (Ika Purnama et al., 2021; Novita & Yuliani, 2016; Rosalina, 2019).

This research aims to explore the impact of marketing automation on customer relationship management strategies and ultimately improve management performance in the

context of B2B MSMEs. Specifically, the research will: Identify the barriers hindering the adoption of CRM and marketing automation in B2B MSMEs, Develop strategies to enhance the digital capabilities of MSMEs and improve their technological understanding, Analyze how CRM can be effectively implemented in B2B MSME businesses by synergizing with marketing automation (Sudarmanto et al., 2023), Evaluate the real impact of implementing marketing automation in CRM on MSME business performance, and Contribute to the knowledge gap on how technology can improve MSME business results and overcome digital transformation barriers to CRM implementation. The findings of this research will provide valuable insights for B2B MSMEs seeking to leverage technology to enhance their customer relationship management practices, improve business performance, and thrive in the digital era (Njiru & Thoronjo, 2023).

Research Method

This study employed a quantitative approach utilizing purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling method that involves selecting subjects based on predetermined criteria. The target population consisted of B2B MSMEs that use Marketing Automation from MarkasBot.id. The sample size was determined using Hair & Ringle(2014) method, resulting in 105 respondents. The instruments used to measure the variables were: Marketing Automation (Benjamin, N & Paraskevi, 2019). B2B Customer Relationship Management (CRM) (Cao & Weerawardena, 2023) and Marketing Performance (Cao & Weerawardena, 2023). Data were collected through a closed online survey or questionnaire distributed via WhatsApp and Telegram. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis was employed to analyze the collected data. Due to the reflective nature of the variables, SEM analysis was conducted using Lisrel 8.80

Results and Discussion

Results

Respondent Characteristics, This stage will show the characteristics of respondents from respondents who filled out this research questionnaire. Respondent characteristics based on gender, age, and education.

Charateristics		
Gender		
Men	74	70.4 per cent
Women	31	29.6 per cent
Age		
Less than 25 years old	81	77,14 per cent
25-34 years old	14	13,33 per cent
35-44 years old	7	6,67 per cent
45-54 years old	2	1,90 per cent
More 55 years old	1	0,96 per cent
Education		
Elementary School	1	0,96 per cent
Junior High School	1	0,96 per cent
Senior High School	88	83,8 per cent
Bachelor Degree	12	11,43 per cent
Master Degree	2	1,90 per cent
Doctoral Degree	1	0,96 per cent

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

CFA is carried out to test a construct that is carried out before testing. CFA is an initial measurement model to test the validation and reliability of all indicators forming latent constructs (Gunarto, 2018; Haryono, 2016; Yanti, 2022). CFA model testing in this study was carried out with one stage (first order).

CFA Model on Variable of Marketing Automation (MA)

The third variable tested with the CFA model is the marketing automation (MA) variable. Below are the results of the Standardized Solution CFA model obtained with the Lisrel 8.80 program.

Chi-Square=0.00, df=0, P-value=1.00000, RMSEA=0.000

Figure 1. Standardized Solution CFA Model Variable Marketing Automation

Source: Data processed in Lisrel 8.80, 2023

The results of the CFA X_2 model validation and reliability test are described in Table 1.

Table 1. Validation and Reliability Test of Marketing Automation Variable

Indicator	λ	λ^2	e	CR	AVE	Ket
MA1	0,810	0,656	0,330	0,833	0,624	Valid and Reliable
MA2	0,760	0,578	0,470			
MA3	0,800	0,640	0,330			
Total	2,370	1,874	1,130			

Table 1 shows that the marketing automation variable CFA model which has 3 indicators is declared valid. This is because all indicators on this variable have factor loading (λ) $>$ 0.5. In addition, in the reliability test, the MA variable has $CR >$ 0.5 (0.833) and $AVE >$ 0.5 (0.624), which means that marketing automation is valid and reliable.

CFA Model on B2B Customer Relationship Management Variable

The fourth variable tested with the CFA model is the B2B CRM variable. Below are the results of the Standardized Solution CFA model obtained using the Lisrel 8.80 program.

Chi-Square=6.10, df=2, P-value=0.04736, RMSEA=0.140

Figure 2. Standardized Solution CFA Model Variables B2B CRM

Source: Data processed in Lisrel 8.80, 2023

The results of the validation and reliability test of the B2B CRM CFA model are described in Table 2.

Table 2. Validation and Reliability of CRM B2B Variable

Indicator	λ	λ^2	e	CR	AVE	Ket
CRM1	0,710	0,504	0,470			
CRM2	0,740	0,548	0,380			
CRM3	0,840	0,706	0,330	0,872	0,633	Valid and Reliable
CRM4	0,880	0,774	0,290			
Total	3,170	2,532	1,470			

Table 2 shows that the CRM B2B variable CFA model which has 4 indicators is declared valid. This is because all indicators on the CRM B2B variable have a loading factor (λ) > 0.5. Then, the results of the CFA model reliability test obtained a CR value > 0.7 (0.873) and AVE > 0.5 (0.633) which means that the CRM B2B variable is valid and reliable.

CFA model on Marketing Performance (MP) Variable

The fifth variable tested with the CFA model is the MP variable. Below are the results of the Standardized Solution CFA model obtained using the Lisrel 8.80 program.

Figure 3. Standardized Solution CFA Model Variable Marketing Performance Initial
Source: Data processed in Lisrel 8.80, 2023

Figure 4. Standardized Solution of the Final Marketing Performance Variable CFA Model
Source: Data processed in Lisrel 8.80, 2023

The results of the validation and reliability test of the CFA MP model are described in Table 3.

Table 3. Validation and Reliability Test of Marketing Performance Variable

Indicator	λ	λ^2	e	CR	AVE	Ket
MP1	0,700	0,490	0,500			
MP2	0,810	0,656	0,340			
MP3	0,700	0,490	0,510	0,783	0,548	Valid and Reliable
Total	2,210	1,636	1,350			

From Figure 3, it can be seen that MP2 is less than 0.5, namely 0.30 so it must be eliminated, the results can be seen in Figure 6. Table 6 shows that 3 indicators have a loading factor (λ) > 0.5, which means that 3 indicators in the MP variable are declared valid. Then, the

CR value > 0.7 (0.783) and AVE > 0.5 (0.548). Therefore, it can be stated that the MP variable is valid and reliable.

Initial Structural Analysis, In the CFA measurement, all variables have been declared valid and reliable. This means that all latent variables are measured properly. The next step is to establish a structural model to find out how the latent variables are related.

Chi-Square=69.50, df=33, P-value=0.00021, RMSEA=0.103

Figure 5. Initial Structural Model
Source: Data processed in Lisrel 8.80, 2023

Table 4. Validation and Reability Test Data on the Initial Model

Indikator	Λ	λ^2	E	CR	AVE	Ket
MA1	0,82	0,67	0,32			
MA2	0,71	0,50	0,50	0,83	0,62	Valid dan Reliabel
MA3	0,83	0,69	0,32			
CRM1	0,73	0,53	0,47			
CRM2	0,81	0,66	0,35	0,87	0,63	Valid dan Reliabel
CRM3	0,81	0,66	0,35			
CRM4	0,82	0,67	0,33			
MP1	0,7	0,49	0,51			
MP2	0,81	0,66	0,35	0,78	0,55	Valid dan Reliabel
MP3	0,71	0,50	0,50			

From Table 4 in testing the overall structural model that 21 indicators tested have been declared valid. This is because all indicators have λ more than 0.5.

GOF on Model Initial Structural

GOF results data on the initial model of the entire structural model in this study are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. GOF on the Initial Model

Goodness-of-fit index	Test Criteria	Value	Test Results
Chi Square	-	71,28	-
Degree of Freedom	-	33	-
P-Value	>0,05	0,00012	Not Fit
RMR	≤ 0,10	0,031	Fit
SRMR	≤ 0,08	0,048	Fit
RMSEA	≤ 0,08	0,10	Not Fit
GFI	> 0,90	0,88	Not Fit
AGFI	> 0,90	0,80	Not Fit
NFI	>0,90	0,95	Fit
IFI	>0,90	0,97	Fit
CFI	>0,90	0,97	Fit
PNFI	>0,90	0,69	Not Fit
PGFI	>0,90	0,53	Not Fit

From Table 5 shows that 6 criteria out of 11 criteria qualify the measurement model that is not good (not fit), especially RMSEA. Based on consensus, the RMSEA criterion is more widely used to determine the suitability of a model (Gunarto, 2018). so that the structural model of this research must be modified. The modified results in this study can be seen in Figure 9.

Figure 6. Final Structural Model
Source: Data processed in Lisrel 8.80, 2023

Validation and Reliability Test of the Final Structural Model, The validation test of the overall final model was carried out to determine the validation of all indicators in this study after being modified. The validation test results of the final model are shown in Table 6

Table 6. Validation and Reliability Test Data on the Final Model

Indikator	λ	λ^2	E	CR	AVE	Ket
MA1	0,80	0,64	0,34	0,83	0,61	Valid dan Reliabel
MA2	0,72	0,52	0,49			
MA3	0,84	0,71	0,35			
CRM1	0,74	0,55	0,51	0,86	0,61	Valid dan Reliabel
CRM2	0,83	0,69	0,40			
CRM3	0,75	0,56	0,31			
CRM4	0,77	0,59	0,31			
MP1	0,68	0,46	0,57	0,76	0,51	Valid dan Reliabel
MP2	0,81	0,66	0,45			
MP3	0,73	0,53	0,55			

From Table 6, it can be seen that all indicators in the final model of the entire model have $\lambda > 0.5$ so that the 20 indicators in this final model have been declared valid. Table 4.10 shows that 5 variables in the final model have a CR value > 0.7 and AVE > 0.5 , which means that the 5 variables in this study are valid and reliable.

GOF Analysis of the Final Model

The GOF results on the final structural model are described in Table 7.

Table 7. GOF in the Final Model

Goodness-of-fit index	Test Criteria	Value	Test Results
Chi Square	-	49,82	-
Degree of Freedom	-	31	-
P-Value	$> 0,05$	0,017	Not Fit
RMR	$\leq 0,10$	0,028	Fit
SRMR	$\leq 0,08$	0,043	Fit
RMSEA	$\leq 0,08$	0,079	Fit
GFI	$> 0,90$	0,91	Fit
AGFI	$> 0,90$	0,84	Not Fit
NFI	$> 0,90$	0,51	Fit
IFI	$> 0,90$	0,96	Fit
CFI	$> 0,90$	0,98	Fit
PNFI	$> 0,90$	0,66	Not Fit
PGFI	$> 0,90$	0,51	Not Fit

Table 7 shows that the structural model formed has met several GOF statistical criteria. 7 criteria out of 11 criteria have met the criteria for a good measurement model (fit), especially RMSEA has met the statistical criteria ≤ 0.08 (RMSEA: 0.079).

R-Square, R-square result this research are shown on the below:

Table 8. R square results

Variables	R Square Result
B2B CRM	0,85
Marketing Performance	0,70

In table 11, it can be seen that the R-square of B2B CRM is 85%, and Marketing Performance is 70%.

Hypothesis Test, All parameters are tested with the t-test statistic. The variable is declared significant if the t-count value is more than 1.96 and if the t-count is less than 1.96 then the variable is not statistically significant. The results of T-Values testing the full model are shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. T-Value Test

Source: Data processed in Lisrel 8.80, 2023

The t-test results are shown in Table 9

Table 9. Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis	Variable Influence	T-Value	Description
H1	MA → CRM	7,76	Significant
H2	CRM → MP	5,88	Significant

Based on Table 12, it can be concluded as follows:

H₁ = There is a positive and significant influence between Marketing Automation (MA) and Customer Relationship Management (CRM), the T-value is 7.76 which is more than 1.96 as the limit value if the variable is significant (accepted).

H₂ = There is a positive and significant influence between Customer Relationship Management (CRM) and Marketing Performance (MP), the T-value is 5.88 which is more than 1.96 as the limit value if the variable is significant (accepted).

Discussion

The Impact of Marketing Automation and Customer Relationship Management (CRM) on Business Performance in B2B

Marketing automation (MA) and CRM are two interconnected concepts that can positively influence each other. MA implementation in CRM enhances customer data management and interactions, leading to improved business performance. This aligns with research by Bandem Bandem Mahatma Wicaksana et al., (2022), who found that VTiger CRM integration positively impacts business performance. Additionally, MA integration with CRM enhances customer interaction personalization. Hasan et al., (2023) analyzed customer relationship management in Moex Ice Cut MSMEs, revealing that MA aids in presenting more relevant customer content, fostering a more personalized and satisfying experience.

The Effect of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) on Marketing Performance in B2B

CRM positively and significantly impacts marketing performance, with a t-value of 5.88. This study demonstrates that MSMEs capable of identifying attractive customers and establishing and maintaining relationships with them to enhance profits tend to exhibit superior marketing performance. This aligns with research by (Cao & Weerawardena, 2023) The theory underlying CRM's influence on marketing performance is based on Teece's dynamic capabilities concept. Companies, or MSMEs in this context, can leverage their dynamic capabilities to generate new knowledge applicable to pursuing their primary competitive strategies. In the CRM context, these capabilities include identifying potential customers, initiating and maintaining relationships with them, and utilizing these relationships to boost customer-level profitability.

Conclusion

Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that marketing automation (MA) and customer relationship management (CRM) have a positive and significant impact on business performance, especially for B2B businesses. MA can improve efficiency in managing customer data and interactions with customers. This can be achieved by automating marketing tasks, such as sending emails, scheduling events, and tracking leads. MA can also improve personalization in customer interactions, so customers feel more valued and appreciated.

CRM, on the other hand, can help businesses to identify potential customers, start and maintain relationships with them, and use those relationships to increase profitability. CRM can also help businesses to understand customer needs and behavior, so businesses can provide better and more relevant service.

When MA and CRM are integrated, these two concepts can complement each other and increase their positive impact on business performance. This integration can help businesses to: Automate marketing and sales tasks more efficiently, Improve personalization in customer interactions, Identify and maintain relationships with potential customers, Understand customer needs and behavior, Increase customer satisfaction, and Increase sales and profits. Therefore, MA and CRM are essential tools for B2B businesses to improve their performance.

References

- Aqiilah. (2022). *Analisis Hubungan E-CRM dengan E-Loyalty Pada E-Commerce Shopee Indonesia dengan Kualitas Chatbot Sebagai Variabel Moderasi*. Universitas Bakrie.
- Bandem Mahatma Wicaksana, N., Putra Githa, D., Agung Ayu Putri, G., Udayana, U., Raya Kampus Unud Jimbaran, J., & Kuta Selatan, K. (2022). Implementasi CRM (Customer Relationship Management) Menggunakan VTiger CRM Pada Perusahaan (Studi Kasus: CV. Maha Sari). *Jurnal Teknik Informatika Dan Sistem Informasi*, 9(4). <http://jurnal>.
- Benjamin, N & Paraskevi, T. (2019). *The Effect of Marketing Automation on the Buying Decisions A quantitative study on SMEs explored through brand awareness and external branding in a B2B context* [Linnaeus University]. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1334295/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- Benjamin, N. etc. (2019). *The Effect of Marketing Automation on the Buying Decisions A quantitative study on SMEs explored through brand awareness and external branding in a B2B context*. Linnaeus University.
- Cao, G., & Weerawardena, J. (2023). Strategic use of social media in marketing and financial performance: The B2B SME context. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 111, 41–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2023.03.007>
- Corsaro, D., Maggioni, I., & Olivieri, M. (2021). Sales and marketing automation in the post-Covid-19 scenario: value drivers in B2B relationships. *Italian Journal of Marketing*, 2021(4), 371–392. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43039-021-00024-x>
- Gunarto, M. (2018). *Analisis Statistik dengan model persamaan struktural (SEM) Teoritis dan Praktis*. Alfabeta.
- Hair, J., & Ringle, C. M. (2014). A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structure Equation Modeling. *SAGE Publication Ltd*, 46(1–2), 184–185.
- Hanaysha, J. R., Al-Shaikh, M. E., & Kumar, P. (2022). An Examination of Customer Relationship Management and Business Sustainability in Small and Medium Enterprises. *International Journal of Customer Relationship Marketing and Management*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJCRMM.300832>
- Harini, S., Pranitasari, D., Said, M., & Endri, E. (2023). Determinants of SME performance: Evidence from Indonesia. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 21(1), 471–481. [https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.21\(1\).2023.40](https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.21(1).2023.40)
- Harisandi, P., Hurriyati, R., & Dirgantari, P. D. (2023). Influence of Brand Equity on Electronic-Word of Mouth Mediated by Brand Love on Shopee E-commerce. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Approach Research and Science*, 2(01 SE-Articles), 83–98. <https://doi.org/10.59653/ijmars.v2i01.357>
- Haryono, S. (2016). Metode SEM untuk Penelitian Manajemen dengan AMOS, LISREL, PLS. In *Badan Penerbit PT. Intermedia Personalia Utama*.
- Hasan, G., Lim, J., Huang, C., Sembiring, E. I., & Syukriansyah, A. (2023). Analisa Customer Relationship Management Es Potong Moex. *Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat Nusantara*, 4(2).
- Humairo, S., & Abidin, Z. (2023). Influence of Gender Diversity, Age, Education, and Work Experience Top Management Team on Intellectual Capital Performance: Empirical Study on Sector Companies Banking in 2021-2022. *Journal of Business Management and Economic Development*, 2(01 SE-Articles), 142–158. <https://doi.org/10.59653/jbmed.v2i01.381>
- Ika Purnama, N., Pratamu Putri, L., & Bahagia, R. (2021). Analisis E-commerce Dalam Membantu Penjualan UMKM di Tengah Pandemi. *EKONOMIKAWAN: Jurnal Ilmu*

- Ekonomi Dan Studi Pembangunan.*
<https://doi.org/10.30596/ekonomikawan.v%vi%i.8503>
- Latifah, K., Waliyansyah, R. R., Saputro, N. D., & Novita, M. (2022). Customer Relationship Management Berbasis Digital pada UMKM di Desa Tengguli, Bangsri, Kabupaten Jepara. *Indonesian Journal of Community Services*, 4(2), 185. <https://doi.org/10.30659/ijocs.4.2.185-192>
- Mero, J., Leinonen, M., Makkonen, H., & Karjaluoto, H. (2022). Agile logic for SaaS implementation: Capitalizing on marketing automation software in a start-up. *Journal of Business Research*, 145(October 2020), 583–594. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.03.026>
- Njiru, M., & Thoronjo, E. (2023). Analysis of Monitoring and Evaluation Practices on Performance of Non-Governmental Organizations' Project in Kiambu County, Kenya. *Journal of Business Management and Economic Development*, 2(01 SE-Articles), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.59653/jbmed.v2i01.308>
- Novita, D., & Yuliani, N. (2016). STUDI KEBERHASILAN UKM MELALUI PERDAGANGAN ONLINE B2B DAN B2C. *KNIT-2 Nusa Mandiri*.
- Parker, P. (2020). *Building vs Buying Marketing Automation Software: Pros and Cons (Infographic) Emarsys*. <https://Emarsys.Com/>. <https://emarsys.com/learn/blog/build-vs-buy-marketing-automation-software-infographic/>
- Ramadhani, W. (2022, September 14). *4 Transformasi Digital yang Bisa Dilakukan UMKM Indonesia*. <https://Kumparan.Com/>.
- Rosalina, V. H. H. (2019). PENGENALAN APLIKASI ELECTRONIC CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT (E-CRM) PADA PELAKU USAHA MIKRO KECIL DAN MENENGAH (UMKM) DESA HARJATANI. *Jurnal Kuat*.
- Saura, J. R., Palos-Sanchez, P., & Blanco-González, A. (2020). The importance of information service offerings of collaborative CRMs on decision-making in B2B marketing. *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 35(3), 470–482. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JBIM-12-2018-0412>
- Sudarmanto, E., Aulia, T. Z., Putri, R. L., & Wulandjani, H. (2023). Urgency of Tax Incentives in Indonesia for Research, Development, and Internationalization of MSMEs. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Approach Research and Science*, 2(01 SE-Articles), 69–82. <https://doi.org/10.59653/ijmars.v2i01.339>
- Thi, P., & Van, H. (2017). *Marketing automation as an enabler in B2B: A study from customer retention perspective*.
- Yanti, P. M. G. (2022). Analysis of Intention Factors Joining Course Using Advertising social media. *Proceedings of the 3rd Asia Pacific International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management*, 3795–3807. <http://ieomsociety.org/proceedings/2022malaysia/610.pdf>
- Yunusa, I., Abubakar, M. B., & Umar, M. M. (2023). Moderating Effect of Independent Directors on the Relationship between Chief Executive Officers Characteristics and Performance of Listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Business Management and Economic Development*, 1(03 SE-Articles), 510–529. <https://doi.org/10.59653/jbmed.v1i03.284>